

Exploring the Intersection of Gender and Christianity in Zimbabwe: Developmental Implications

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ABSTRACT

All socio-cultural institutions are pervaded around gender issues. They typically indisposition the way people of varying sexes perceive themselves, associate or portray with others at any given circumstance and time. In Zimbabwe gender matters affects things like social class, amassing of property, inheritance, behaviour, occupation and accountability, the family set up, and community at large. While Zimbabwe is patriarchal society, evidence shows that women and girls are vanquished and demoted to the milieu as mere objects rather than subjects in different spheres of life. This scenario has developed an indisposed correlation between men and women in the country's societies because of the illusory disproportionate merit the males always have over their female counterpart. The dire tension has also deterred harnessing of both women and girls potentials in development process. Many people in Zimbabwe have embraced Christianity's teachings and practices since its inception, thus shifting their cultural values and traits. Christian churches have multiplied phenomenally within the past century, and depict the few Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) that endure operating even during armed conflict. Christian organisations have command and effect, for religion has the potential to influence behaviour, facilitate societal change, and provide societal solidarity and cohesion. Christianity's conduct is a powerful resource for marginalized women and girls in Zimbabwe for they can fully participate in all spheres of life. In this connection, the study probed challenges and conflicts connected on gender questions and how the Christianity advent has accustomed other faith based organizations to interrogate the concern, so as to attain the comprehensive developmental practices and policies in Zimbabwe. Phenomenological research method was used to provide objective findings. Write-up upholds for a synchronous; holistic and committed viewpoint, by the Church to mitigate the gender difference. Though research focus is on Zimbabwe, findings can be universally applied in other varying contexts.

Keywords: Christianity; Gender; Gender links; Development; Socio-cultural organisations.

1.1 Introduction

The anthropoid environment is always tormented because of gender concerns especially where there is interaction between women and men. Such an association that exists between men and women in socio-anthropological settings which are household, wealth, electioneering, religion and education is greatly frequently impaired with among others dominance, alienation, discrimination and perversion (Charamba, 2015). Pathetic of them being gender dominance, a paradox that slants to authoritative standing in Zimbabwe. Etymologically, patriarchy precisely means a framework of authority whereby control or dominion is disseminated unfairly endorsing men over women (Waters, 2019). Men are respected and valued greatly at the expense of their women counter-part in the community setting, autonomous of the accomplishments of women in question. This segregation is chiefly expressed by emotional, bodily and devotional exploitation of females that sometimes causes sense of discomfort; humiliation, and at times deace (Ali, 2020). To nosedive such unhealthy affairs of females, Charamba (2015) opines that, this habit seems more frequent in most churches, bearing into deliberation how the Churches are being applauded as the adjudicators of fairness and justice, where the oppressed ones seek refuge, and house of atrocity victims. Notwithstanding, some other churches gratify ugly gender dominance and discrimination which negatively impact on development processes.

Gender-inclined vexations have contrived varying pursuits of and the companionship that exist between males and females since scriptural times (Okoli and Okwuosa, 2020). Everlastingly, such state of affairs were viewed and widely allowable as how people must behave in various Churches and in the communities as a whole with doctrinal support, although it appears very hostile with regard to instruction of Jesus, his being, expedition and the congregation that unfolded after the death and rebirth. It further goes contrary to human impartiality of equivalent integrity and privileges for everyone as prescribed by Sustainable Development goal five of 2015. Regrettably, most of those bearing the gender dominance are women and girls in both private and public spectrum of life. Girls and women, for example, represent the topmost populace of congregants, but in many instances both are denied approval to aspire to the uppermost phase of Church command, or participate in higher strategic-making boards (Charamba, 2015). Alternatively, these women are treated as objects and in most cases confided to the backdrop. Besides Christian sphere, Bako and Syed (2018) reverberate that ‘belittling women and girls in economic advancement or

growth, and social and political spectrums is a global scenario'. This is more pronounced in most developing country like Zimbabwe, which 'Despite the fosterage of the United Nations' Convention on the *Elimination of all forms of discrimination against women* in 1985, and similar local policies such as the *National gender policy* of 2006, disparities are nevertheless visible mainly due to a multifarious of societal and fundamental provocations', (Mapuranga, 2019:125). Such unfolding of events has obstructed women and girls involvement in both private and public spaces with sedate ramifications for the economic and human personnel development of Zimbabwe.

Such situations distinctly demonstrate graveness of gender imbalance as a real arsenal of vilification; despotism and inhibition of the women-kind. However due to changing times, the Church being the solo cornerstone of Christianity, is expected to go through change as well. Taking into cognizance of Pauline epistles, which evidently shows, how Jesus and Paul (see, for example, 1 Corinthians 7:1–6), associated with both, females and males without discreteness. Men and women in question both were obedient to his tutoring and disported loyalty or allegiance by divining and providing help to the Lord, (as outlined in Romans 16). Ayuba (1998) has postulated that:

Christianity through Jesus reinstated the earliest companionship among humankind as entrenched at human creation time by the Lord. Within gospel passages, Christ obliterated all markings of male dominance and female subject-hood and positioned all on equal footing. In His teaching and divining, Jesus acknowledged everyone and denounced everything that seek to segregate contrary to any group, particularly females. He even discarded the rule of infidelity which castigated females and not males (John 8:1–12). (p. 102)

In other words it was a clear indication that there is no more high-handed of gender in all spheres of life. Irregardless of sexes both men and women do poses equal blessings with regards to offerings and talents which can be fully utilised to improve the entire world, hence they must be accorded equal chance to showcase and surpass themselves in all spheres of life that affect them in one way or the other, (Okoli and Okwuosa, 2020). With regard to this, this research contemplates that for Zimbabwe to attain sustainable development goal 5 by 2030, the female gender should to be given her deserved spot denuded of bigotry or injustice and marginalisation. To attain such a

milestone, the vibrant force of Christianity, must be found earnestly patronising human rights, equitability, impartiality and tranquility in Zimbabwe, and globe as a whole. Christianity should be in the vanguard of challenging disparities and advancing equality and women empowerment at all cost.

1.2 The State of Gender in Zimbabwe: Disparities, Linkages, and Role Expectations.

Understanding divergences of gender in all facets of life could be done by probing sex and gender as different entities. Sex may be alluded to mean an ‘anatomy of an individual’s reproductive system’, while gender could be seen as secondary sex attributes from which social roles are based on the sex of the person (gender role) or personal identification of one’s own, (Virginia, 2019). In other ways, while gender is a socially fashioned definition of men and women, sex is the biological characteristics of men and women, (Virginia, 2019). Kabeer (2019:11) has this to say;

"Gender is seen as the process by which individuals who are born into biological categories of male or female become the social categories of men and women through the acquisition of locally-defined attributes of masculinity and femininity".

The biblical narratives mostly pertaining the creation stories and the fall of man clearly demonstrate how gender related circumstances emanated. Premised in the first assertion on creation history, it is noted that, men and women were created at one go and both were given command upon everything on earth (Genesis 1:27), thus composing them equal. The second formation version alluded that, the female was created from the male (Genesis 2:22). In other version as noted by Charamba (2015), there appears to have a huge gap of vacuousness and inadequacy available with the male prior to the formation of female. Consequently, women’s formation was meant to consolidate men. But regardless of this symbolism on equitable companionship of man and woman, Uchem (2018:145), ascertained that the image of God is portrayed within the male and not in the female, for male is the commencement and end of female. Such initial suppositions regarding the ascendancy of the man over the woman altered and assembled most heritages that vanquished and demoted females to the backdrop, thus impacting the affinity intermediate to man and woman. Amidst several Zimbabwean households, the social setting upon which most people command is patriarchy. This patriarchal set-up exhibits men as

leaders of households while females and children fall within their jurisdiction and discipline. On this regard, most of the responsibilities are designated to representatives of diverse households in relation to their biological make-up, standings, dexterities and expertise. Having such type of power formation, it clearly demonstrates that males are empowered more than females in various life facets.

Considering this male head structure of most African societies, Chinweizu (2018:69) cited by Okoli and Okwuosa (2020) postulates that ‘in the face of patriarchy is matriarchy (rule of mothers)’. He additionally opines that ‘patriarchy may be socially and publicly endorsed, but matriarchy is the law of life’. The subsequent utterances from Chinweizu cast more discernment into this pronouncement: ‘my husband may be the head of the house; I am the neck that turns the head – an American housewife’. The reasoning here there is that life will be fragmentary whenever there is no the harmonising duty of women.

Going through some biblical narratives, one concludes that Jesus associated with both irregardless of sexuality issues. Females and males were both compassionate to the teachings and disported loyalty by divining and aiding to the Lord. Gasque (2020) equitably concludes that in the Holy Book the ‘conservative stance’ emphasises capitulation and enslavement. For instance (see Ephesians 5:23, 1 Corinthians 11:3, and 1 Timothy 5:8, etcetera). Gasque 2020:

A woman’s role in relation to home, church and society is to be in submission to her husband (or to male leadership) and to be dependent upon him/them. She has her own sphere and freedom to exercise her spiritual gifts, but it is ultimately under the leadership of the male who takes the lead in the home and in the church, that her gifts are expressed. This view is based on hierarchical understanding of the relationship of God to Christ to man to woman, stemming from Paul’s argument in Corinthians 11:1–16, where he presents what we might call a chain of hierarchy: Christ is subject to the Father, man to Christ, and woman to man. (p. 1)

Such, according to Gasque (2020), is the pronunciation of the conservative view. He further narrates that:

The egalitarian view argues that there is no scriptural reason for women not to share in leadership in the Church, or to participate in a marriage relationship that is based on a

principle of mutual submission and interdependent love. The accent in the egalitarian view is on mutual submission, not on the submission of one party to the other, but each party to one another – both in the church and in the home. (p. 1)

The unfortunate part is, if one looks at the Holy Book, it distinctly exhibits that it was penned by most males, for males and about males. According to Jacqueline Dorr (2017) cited in Charamba et al (2024), women in various sections certainly come out in the Bible rather in marginal responsibilities that chiefly suffice to develop and support achievements stories associated with men. For illustration, Okoli and Okwuosa (2020) posit that, men authored regarding females portraying like they literally involve them within the community. However, their familiarity of women was tinted more by masculinity animosity and bewilderment which are eminently patriarchal and could not be justified to be ‘Lord-animated’. Patriarchal settings infrequent cases seem to buttress and elucidate that which is beneficial for its continuity hence women and girls remain objects in varying circumstances. Carbajal (2018:2) for instance, extracted a Bible reading demonstrating that the ‘wife lacks mastery over the body she owns, but the husband control both’ (1 Corinthians 7:4). The dilemma, pitched with regard to that is that, ‘most persons neglect the subsequent component of that passage, which is correspondingly also the husband does not have command over his own body, but the wife does’, (Carbajal, 2018:2). But stunningly, the latter is always overlooked. The ‘entire passage shows that men and women are accountable for one another. Carbajal (2018) further noted that:

Bible treats the couple as equal partners, not as a hierarchy. Thus, the Bible is used to interpret women’s role in society. This women’s societal role has been institutionalized, resulting in biased treatment in the workplace and other spectrum of life.

The model of leadership in both spheres be it private or public has been compatible with manful attributes. Benefactions made by women and girls in various settings do not necessarily receive an appraisable recognition in the developmental process and are banished because they are recognised as frail or mere subordinates in the society. In Zimbabwe, for example, females provide the engine of the rural economy mostly in agricultural sector. Available data clearly shows that over 80% of the economically viable population of women are employed in the agricultural sector, (Chitando, 2019:19). So to ‘establish a vibrant; efficient; sustainable and unbiased agricultural

sector, women and girls in Zimbabwe need not to be disregarded in decision-making process’, Chitando (2019:19).

1.3 Gender Oppression in Zimbabwe: Causes, Consequences and Developmental Implications.

Patriarchal organizational structures characterizing most African states are behind the rampant scenario of gender imbalances currently underway in the region. This is more pronounced in most organizational set ups in Zimbabwe; even where the bulk of members are women, the top leadership will be comprised of men. Regrettably, such a provision can be comfortably justified to be Almighty’s accord and legal entity, and various passages contained in the Holy book could be cited to substantiate the masculinity related points, (Charamba et al, 2024). For example, in the Holy Book, the Almighty is acknowledged as being Father of people like Abraham, Isaac and Jacob, but the acknowledgement of their wives was never mentioned. On the other note, in the pessimistic ideology, the same Bible mentioned Delilah (Judge 16), Jezebel (1 Kings 21), Bathsheba (2 Samuel 11) and Eve (Genesis 3) as persistently criticised for the ‘down-fall or collapse’ of the glorious man of God and humankind, (Okoli and Okwuosa, 2020). Despite the fact that such a scenario is regarded as arbitrary to women, paradoxically the Church itself sees it burdensome to go contrary or hostile to these verses concluding that they were documented as authentic realities. ‘Men and women’s responsibilities are consequently much distinguished and also unhinged’ in almost every part the life facets.

Klingorova and Havlíček (2019:3) posit that, it is more imperative to spotlight that ‘at times there are some discrepancies between idiosyncratic constraints, which relates to proclamations by any particular religion (equality of males and females insight of God) and pragmatic constraint’, which entails the real responsibility of women Vis-a- Vis men in our daily family settings. Whenever such imbalances relating to gender issues pops up, it usually discourages averse the advancement of balanced liberties to women which in turn cause disgruntlement, violence, bitterness, irritation, alienation, dispiritedness, and certainly disproportionate supportable improvement and impoverishment. Okeke (2020) argues that sustainable development demands a meaningful engagement of both women and girls at every phase of development process. For any meaningful

endeavor to be successful, it therefore requires a collective approach where women and girls fully participate, hence gender equity in this regard will become fundamental.

Gender favoritism or bigotry usually leads to women and girls oppression and overall impedes development process in both private and public spheres. In Zimbabwe, this is more pronounced in cultures such as Shangani and Varemba, and it is believed to have health implications on females, (for example, genital mutilation); albeit of country's joint commitments to all the treaties on both women and girl-child's rights. Charamba et al (2024) postulates that extensive spectrum of detrimental traditional and cultural habitudes are still pervasive in many societies across Africa as a whole and Zimbabwe is not yet spared. These practices have devastating consequences on the health of both women and girls, and in most cases difficulties like impotence and fruitlessness usually emanate from the harm caused by this practice. Notable incidences of diseases are also contracted during such malpractices. Eneh and Nkamnebe (2019) postulated that, from seven years of age:

Other discriminatory social practices, which place the girl-child at a greater disadvantage over the boy-child, begin to manifest. These practices include unequal gender division of work and access to leisure, early marriage and female disinheritance. (p. 41)

Concerning imbalance fractionalisation of work, Bawa (2017) accurately pronounces that in a family setting, the woman is expected to provide food at the table and sole bread winner, child bearer, child minder and also overlooks the schooling activities of the kids regardless of her restrained capabilities and educational standing in any given society. Without doubt, such malpractices negatively affect the health of women and further entrench on their constitutional legal provisions as well as their anticipated benefaction towards development process in Zimbabwe.

1.4 Gender Justice and the Zimbabwe Christian Church

More than two billion people in the world subscribe to Christianity as their main religion, (Bawa, 2017). The Christian revelation gist on certitudes contemplating the whole life of Christ, that is, from birth to resurrection times. Slick (2020:1) observes that 'it is a relationship with the true and living God through the person of Jesus Christ by whom we are forgiven of our sins and dodge the

rightful discernment of God'. Jesus' tutoring is much focused on co-existence, peace and love for one another. Pauline epistle in the book of Galatians, distinctly recorded that the Spirit always bears fruits like love, joy, peace, forbearing,

For clarity purpose, the concepts of Church, Christian Church and Christianity will be interchangeably used in this discourse. The place of Christianity could be examined on what Christian Church has been able to foster to improve the lots of women and girls, thereby empowering them to meaningfully contribute their quota in the developmental process, and progress in Zimbabwean society at large.

Benevolence; friendliness; trustworthiness; kindness and self-control (Galatians 5:22). This Pauline epistle coached more against egocentricity, self-esteem, apprehension, annoyance, brutality as a clear indication that both males and females are at equal footing in all respect.

Notwithstanding the goodies in Christianity, the real status of women due to Christian practices today speaks a different language or rather it is more complicated to the deterrent of development process in any given society, (Charamba, 2015). Within the religious narratives, 'the utterance of females is infrequently listened to, mainly because of the patriarchal complexion of the communities where these denominations evolved, and which ultimately suppressed most of the alterations in the position of females activated by new denomination', (Klingorova and Havlíček, 2019:2). Koeppen- Schomerus *et al.* (2010) opines that, despite the fact that African conservative community was completely men-led in creation (male characterised the domineering emissary in the household and females played aiding duties to men), women in most cases were cherished with much respect. But, Mwije (2020) posits that due to the inception of contemporary approach by the government, trade and education by colonialists, women has become marginalized and their male counter-part continue to enjoy the favor.

In Zimbabwean context, distinguishable accomplishments were recorded and attainable by most Faith Based institutions. It is very difficult to separate the faith based institution from facets that concerns gender because it is made up of congregants of different sexes. Consequently, it is obligated to be encountered with varied provocations of gender ascendancy like any other human organization, (Charamba etal, 2024). The divergence, nonetheless, possibly will emanate because the Church itself is considered to be sacred organisation and regarded as been the union of all

God's servants, who adores people equitably and unreservedly, irregardless of sexuality, (Charamba, 2015). On the basis of this setting, Faith Based Institution repositates to the confrontations of gender discrepancy and discrimination through varying ways as given in the following section.

1.4.1 Pre and Post marriage counselling

The Faith Based Institution has established a pre and post matrimony counseling schedules considering that issues of violence and gender disparities commonly take centre stage within the families and chiefly between couples. These programmes aim to educate couples on how best they can overcome such disgusting challenges, Charamba et al (2024). In most scenarios, these Christian churches pay particular attention to intending couples on spot-light issues whose chances of falling prey to gender discrepancies such as fruitlessness; physical women bushing and human sexuality issues are high. Genotype and compatibility tests are usually requested from the couples as part of the counseling session. Consistently, the couples involved are advised to clearly demonstrate and unveil their compatibility wills disclosed to their counter-parts. Okoli and Okwuosa, (2020) further postulated that, in Roman Catholic Church, for instance, the leaders make it known to aiming partners that their marriage is null and void if they deliberately hide any fundamental issues like barrenness, impotence and loss of womb in the case of the woman, or any serious illness from their partners. In fact, 'any of the partners deceived by malice, perpetrated to obtain consent, concerning some quality of the other partner which, by its very nature can gravely disturb the partnership of conjugal life', makes the marriage null and void, (Okoli and Okwuosa, 2020).

1.4.2 Podium preaching

Contemporary, various teachers of the Word mostly within Orthodox and Pentecostal churches are now becoming more gender sensitised in their teachings and practices, unlike yesteryears when they preferred the subject hypothesised. Sensitisation curriculum taught at various seminars and most of the Theological colleges in the country has drastically led to a positive development initiative in as far as gender issues are concerned. Remediated moralistic entails that every humankind, male or female should be equitably acknowledged, esteemed and applauded as persons created in the likeness and resemblance of God. Despite the difference in sexual standing, they are equal and complimentary to each other before the creator. God loves all humankind

unequivocally and thus, everyone is to be awarded the glorious chance to practice and advance their capabilities irregardless of sexuality. Due to this contemporary approach, preachers and teachers of the Word are also fast matching the new sacred curriculum which seeks to deconstruct the yesteryears belief and standing, hence promotion of complementarities amongst the sexes. Due to new gender sensitizing curriculum, the preaching and teaching of the Word is now revolving on bold denouncement on harmful cultural practices that oppress women and girls in the church and societies at large. Some of these practices include, widowhood concerns; wife inheritance; child-pledging and female private-parts mutilation, (Pemunta and Alubafi, 2016:123). Huge attention is placed on the issues like practices and teachings that promotes collaborative esteem or honor and profound love for both people irrespective of their sexes. Today, most Christian churches such as FIFM, AFM, and Alliance church are giving women a better chance to stand and preach the Word on the pulpit and also ordain them as leaders in various capacities, (Charamba, 2015). Such a scenario has immensely contributed to the betterment of gender issues and development process in Zimbabwe. Today most women Christian church goers in Zimbabwe are participating in greater numbers in the public spectrum like politics without fear of the patriarchal connotation.

1.4.3 Symposium and awareness programs

Due to high incidences of atrocity or inhumanity companioned with gender disparities in both homes and communities plus the bad standings they form on the church in society, many religious groups like Reformed Church in Zimbabwe, Forward in Faith Ministries, Apostolic Faith Mission in Zimbabwe etcetera have endorsed colloquium (seminar) and illuminative sessions to repress such disgraceful or humiliating scenario, (Charamba etal, 2024). Today churches through their leadership always organize some convivial meetings at which several subject specialists deliver short addresses on a topic or related topics. The women rights to their body; issues of self-defense and physical violence; their subservience; promotion of educating females and provoking exercises that women vulnerable to sexual infections are the main concerns emphasised by these newly established programmes. Also to note is, these same programmes clearly promote women's sexual and reproductive rights both within and outside churches. Sunday school learning sessions and catechism groups are conducted to enlighten varying households on how people must peacefully live for the uprightness within their respective households without blemishing one another or whichever way, (Okoli and Okwuosa, 2020).

1.4.5 Priestly teachings

Most religious affiliations in Zimbabwe prescribed various answers to gender discrepancies; victimisation and marginalisation of women within their respective churches by documenting pastoral letters, church weekly and monthly magazines, mission statements and lessons contrary to the maltreatment. The Catholic Church and other Pentecostal churches such as Forward in Faith Ministries, Apostolic Faith Mission in Zimbabwe, Alliance Church etcetera have exclusively, over the years, responded contrary to the mistreatment on females by means of the Church leadership's stance and teachings, (Charamba et al, 2024). Pope Paul VI (1988) has mentioned these words while closing the Second Vatican Council:

The hour is coming, in fact has come, when the vocation of women is being acknowledged in its fullness, the hour in which women acquire in the world an influence, an effect and a power never hitherto achieved. That is why, at this moment when the human race is undergoing so deep a transformation, women imbued with a spirit of the Gospel can do so much to aid humanity in not falling.' (p. 1)

The appeal by Pope John Paul II was one of the vibrant reference point which his entire administration has made known to the congregants and world at large. In his pontifical message, according to the *Mulieris Dignitatem*, (2019) concerning the decency and mission for females, he echoed the essentiality of granting females their deserved position and giving them due respect globally. Pope's utterance has prolonged to resonate and reproduced not only within Catholic dioceses of the world but in other Christian churches, so as to address the gender impartiality in all Faith Based Organisations. Doctor, (2020) highlighted that, in 2010, the conference held by Zimbabwe Council of Churches (ZCC) in Harare reiterated the Faith Based Organisations' undying support and defence for every right that negatively infringe on all persons irregardless of sexuality. The organisation made more emphasis on the rights that touch on matters like prostitution; slavery; gender; human trafficking; (especially the selling of women and children), and humiliating operating situations, where persons are handled like scanty objects meant for profiteering and not accountable subjects'. The colloquium further implicate the present day government for poorly performing or exercising its mandate to deter such bastardising circumstances which most Zimbabweans are suffering from. The matter has literally become part

of all the gathering's communiqué as Zimbabwe endures to be tormented or bedeviled by brutalising gender related rights which are also impeding development processes.

1.4.6 Encompassing explanation of scriptural passages

Scriptures interpretation and encompassing language have become central and outstanding in various denominations in Zimbabwe. Contrary to yesteryears, when precisely these Biblical elucidation of passages advanced gender oppression against women, authorities of various Churches today are administering some gender powerful passages sensitively and skillfully, (Charamba et al, 2024). An exemplary to this is John Paul II's comment in Genesis 3:16: God said to the woman 'your desire will be for your husband, and he will rule over you'. For the Holy Pontiff, in his Apostolic Letter *Mulieris Dignitatem* (Considering the self-respect and mission of females) this does not translate to mean that male and female are not at par, or the latter be a chattel to the former.

There is harmonious or concordant proclamations from religious sects especially leaders, that passages which calls for subordination of women to their male counterparts must not be a vindication or an apology to restrain women, or intimidation to allow oppression, (see Ephesians 5:23–24, 1 Timothy 2:11–14 and 1 Timothy 2:8–15). The fact that these explanations or utterances were communicated to a specified group or congregation at a certain time (were context specific) and, thus, impossible to be universally and all over irrevocable to other assemblies, (Charamba, 2015). In addition to that, those were not accurate words of Jesus, and thus, cannot be said to be rudimental, or a true yardstick that signifies Christian ethos (ibid). Such sentiments or assertion are totally opposed to a marriage setting whereby whatsoever is said to one of the partners pertains to the other since they are now resemble one and not two.

God-fearing union is a solemn agreement that manifest between a male and female 'declaring their dedication to respect; to love plus to adore each other in every life's encompassing episodes before God', (Ellicott, 2017). In this regard, whatever that may cause infringement on such a particular union-ship with regards to gender supremacy, discrimination and oppression of accomplice is a contravention of this agreement or contract. It tears off the conjugality pledge and setting in any given situation.

Due to commencement of encompassing language and explanation of the scriptures, various congregants and non-congregants become cognisant that the scriptures should not be used as a tool to disregard wrongful or segregate anyone due to sexuality. Jesus' redemption together with biblical passages are encompassing and not unique to any sexuality, race, humankind or language. Such knowledge and understanding of the sacred passages immensely contributed to gender parity and spearhead sustainable development in all spectrums in Zimbabwe.

1.4.7 Church partnering with government and non-profit agencies

The Faith Based Institutions in Zimbabwe has various organs such as Peace and Reconciliation; Zimbabwe Association of Churches (ZAC) and other constitutional sections that partner with both non-profit agencies and government, and are devoted to females and children mostly regarded as endangered in various societal set ups, (Charamba et al, 2024). Most of the upcoming Christian faith based churches have since established or run various harborages and safe homes where they target to accommodate sexually maltreated women and girls; provide counseling sessions and advance their cases to various courts against their assailants. These church denominations in collaboration with various agencies sometimes consider putting up some paid advertisements in the media against pernicious or wickedness discharged to girls and women. In most cases they spot-light the country's legal provisions for the avoidance of gender discrimination and dominance, and the far-reaching punitive action for defaulters, (Okoli and Okwuosa, 2020). The agencies together with other Churches also managed to set up some crime stoppers or help line numbers committed to victims to be in touch for help at any given time. Campaign for Female Education (CAMFED) and Msasa Project are also collaborating the effort these churches are putting towards a gender inequality free Zimbabwe.

1.5 The impact of gender imbalance on development process

Developmental processes in Zimbabwe became influenced by the spiraling wave of gender injustice in both private and public spectrum. The aftermath of these injustices are foregoing stated.

1.5.1 Socio-economic effect on gender and development

Meaningful human sustainable development may remain a far-fetched day dream without fully addressing gender equality and women empowerment in most African states, (Doctor, 2020). In

as much as women's pursuits are underpaid and undervalued, their reliance on their husbands for their economic welfare will continue to exist, thus breeding an enslavement syndrome that will extinguish or rubber-stamp any notable duty they might have done in the manufacturing of affluent within their households and society at large. Denying women things like equal rights, job security and benefits and employment opportunities, which are accessible to their male counterparts, they will always stumble below the datum penury margin, (Charamba, 2015). Such is mainly due to their impotence to deliver the fundamental essentials that make up a life for the entire family. Sibani (2017:438) noted that 'when one climbs the company profile ladder, low percentage of females will be visible'. Such was also coequally said out by Sibani (2017) that:

Women take a number of disadvantages in paid work, tend to be paid less than men, are more likely to be in part-time work, and tend to do particular type of jobs usually those with a low status. (p. 438)

Besides such a backdrop, Sibani (2017) posits that:

The important role and contribution of women in the process of development was not recognised and consequently nothing was done to harness the potential of the women folk in the Zimbabwean quest for meaningful sustainable development process. (p. 438)

1.5.2 Political impact on gender and development

Coming to political sphere, women's participation in self-governing processes that is, enrollment of political parties, elections and nomination into strategic policy-crafting placements is still lagging miles behind western world and not uplifting continentally and Zimbabwe marks one of the lowest in such accomplishment. Chitando (2020) is of the view that:

From contemporary perspectives in Zimbabwe, it would appear that women had never been influential in the realm of Zimbabwean politics. Both in the past and present democratic dispensation, there has been and there is still, some fair share of recognition of the increasing role of women in the Zimbabwean society, that the place of women in politics during the pre-colonial period is sufficiently familiar. During the colonial period, women asserted and expressed themselves politically in some sects of the society though insignificantly. Some women who make political marks at that period included Mbuya

Nehanda Nyakasikana of the 1896 and Magret Dongo of the famous Women Democrats. It is however worthy to mention here that, though women enjoyed power and higher level of authority in Zimbabwe, men have always been dominant in the political structure with women playing sedentary roles as voiceless; objects; subordinate and inferior partners. (pp. 24-25)

Notwithstanding clear signs and prospects for escalated resemblance of women in political supremacy in the country unfold to be stalwart, available statistics released on political illustration of women in Zimbabwe unpacked by Mapuranga (2020) demonstrates that gender earnings in the last ten years or so have not imaged much in the rank of women's meaningful involvement in political authoritative positions. Such a situation was attributed mainly to women's dire shortage of resources, societal suppositions, traditionalist family raising, lack of quality education, traditional values and norms, lack of professional experience and expertise, ageism and physical violence perpetrated on women, and inequitable duties designated to women in most political institutions.

1.5.3 Religious impact on gender and development

When appraising man or woman administration in modern-day Christianity, 'it is crucial to make differentiations based on denominational positions (for example Forward in Faith Ministries embraces a distinguishable viewpoint to the Roman Catholic Church and the African Instituted Churches (AICs) like African Apostolic). Mapuranga (2020) 'posits that 'in contrast to the Forward in Faith Ministries, the Roman Catholic Church, and SDA etcetera nevertheless confines the priesthood or pastor hood to male gender perse'. Joynes, (2021) has noted that:

Pope John Paul II's 1988 apostolic letter Mulieris Dignitate acknowledged the growing need to address the role of women in the Roman Catholic Church, and concluded that women are equal to men, but different. He affirmed the important place of women with extensive reference to key roles played by female figures in the Old and New Testaments. Nevertheless, despite such positive affirmations, he concluded that in calling only men as his apostles, Christ acted in a completely free and sovereign manner. In doing so, he exercised the same freedom with which, in all his behaviour, he emphasized the dignity and the vocation of women, without conforming to the prevailing customs and to the traditions

sanctioned by the legislation of the time. Notwithstanding this position, there remain a significant group who continue to campaign for women priests in the Catholic Church. (p. 1)

The research conducted by Banda (2019) in Zimbabwe has indicated how pastorate issues are harnessed by male gender, and presence of huge percentage of men as clergyman compared to females in the Orthodox religious sects but significant changes have been witnessed in Pentecostal churches in the country. Religious sects such as Apostolic Faith Mission (AFM); Forward in Faith Ministries (FIFM); Alliance church etcetera ordains women as pastors, Evangelists, Bishops and elders, Charamba (2015). This is totally opposite to Roman Catholic, Seventh Day Adventist and several African Instituted churches (AICs) like Johanne Masowe, Zviratidzo, and African Apostle (ibid). Okoli and Okwuosa, (2020) also observed that, in the old-fashioned setting, there is overwhelming attestation that most women perform duties as goddess and foreseer, but capacity vary greatly as compared to men. For example, the administration of certain ceremonies and rituals men have the supremacy in various Orthodox churches. Okoli and Okwuosa, (2020) opines that such is visible during times of offering prayers and kolanuts (*Cola acuminata*) breaking, or in the midst of cascading of sacrifice to the fore-fathers. Within the Muslims settings, it is inconceivable that females should carry out responsibilities of an Imam, hence their huge numbers are found within Purdah settings. Due to masculine interpretation of certain passages in both the Holy Bible and the Koran, gross religious practices that are discriminatory to women and girls in Zimbabwe are more rampant. Women's religious potentials therefore are inadequately harnessed due to such high levels of exclusion. Christianity system in Zimbabwe are anticipated to defend women liberation and freedom, provided the affinity that exist between church and community is mutual in nature. All things being equal as expected, such a scenario will positively help women to bestow their quota in all processes of development in Zimbabwe as a whole, (Charamba, 2015).

1.6 Recommendations

Below are some endorsements that will minister as part of the duties of Christianity in gender affairs in Zimbabwe.

1.6.1 Sincere Initiatives by the Church

The Church should develop theologically based material through their mission statements that accentuates gender equivalency and women empowerment at all phases of Church hierarchy or entire leadership. The Church should be open and always usher the truth via its teachings and practices about women's oppression and violence, the consequential to the defaulters without fear of, or compromising their voice. Adoption of non-tolerance and denunciation of it by the Church can serve as a resource for sufferers and perpetrator at all levels. Moreover, the Church must put in place castigating interventions which are serious against any form of gender domination or inequality on members who indulge in it.

1.6.2 Diversity

Different viewpoints, ideas and life insights which both men and women have, will enable them to find long lasting solutions to their problems and always enhance a progressive communal living. Hence, if the Church advocates gender discrepancy in all its spectrum, it will not merely add value in top church's formational organization, but the public sphere of the world will benefit. There are several issues men usually do pretty well than their women counterparts and vice versa, thus, entailing equivalence in the society and development arena. In the Church set up, all humankind be it a man or a woman, girl or boy must be viewed or recognised as an appliance for the achievement of the sacred Will rather than being seen as subject and object respectively. In the Christian ethics, this is the essentiality of human creation and salvation as noted by Paul in the Galatians.

1.6.3 The Church as a 'Beacon of hope and Transformation'

Customarily, most religious sects were known for performing an authoritative wave to transfigure attitudes and behaviors in different communities as in the matter against colonisation (though contested), servitude and separatism or apartheid (for example in South Africa). Due to the respect attached to Church, it is therefore necessary to consider it as a bona fide emissary of optimistic turnaround of things. As pointed out by Onwunta (2021):

Since the realm of God is about justice, the Church cannot adequately preach about equity when the females in the Church are handled cruelly. The Church should indeed be great emissary of transformation.... By so doing the Church can nurture a community of faith that can give hope to

the hopeless. This community of faith is one that will not only sympathise with the poor but also empathise and work in solidarity with them. (pp. 120–121)

Gender inequality and disempowerment of women must be certainly viewed by the Church as offence against humankind. It is an atrocity behavior that contravenes all what the religious sect meant for and teaches. As such, this must not only entrusted to scriptural implications but, basically, everyone in the Church should be part of this if meaningful development process is to be achieved.

1.6.4 Articulate monitoring and evaluation personnel

Comprehensive programmes that act as a guideline must be put in place and followed by Church leaders in order to realize their objective of zero tolerance to gender domination and women disempowerment. Such a noble idea must not be left to the individual leaders but to the whole Church so that accomplishment will be smoothly. This must also be viewed as the blue-print of the Church always, and should be an encompassing one irregardless of sexuality. This will become an obligation to be taken by the Church itself train personnel to monitor and evaluate progress, particularly forthcoming generation Church commanders, who are mandated to canonise much of their absolute time and being to this redemption expedition.

1.6.5 Building Human Assets through Strategic Investment

Government together with advocacy agencies should make effort to address the plight of women's democratic predispositions and full delineation in Zimbabwe. Achieving this can be managed by constituting national legal framework which can easily expedite women's admittance to electoral and appointive, policy-crafting ranks. Additionally, providing women and girls with financial assistance, educating them, mentoring them and expanding their networks will be of mammoth contribution for their political endeavors, (Bawa, 2017). NGOs and CBOs should also compliment government effort to increase women's political consciousness, sensitization and engagement in both private and public sphere. With regard to such a situation, Okoli and Okwuosa (2020) also highlighted that, enfranchisement of women politically will positively improve the ratification and application of legal provisions that seek to exterminate all detrimental customary systems apportioned upon them. Increased advocacy for women's rights will also be attained and felt only when women get empowered politically.

1.7 Conclusion

This write-up has divulged Faith Based Institutions endowed in Christian beliefs, gender matters and developmental processes in Zimbabwe. It takes into considerations the inducements and consequences of gender discrepancy and segregation within the developmental arena of Zimbabwe as an aspect to be attended to and annihilate by the Church, since it is against to the persona of Jesus' Church and the mission embedded within his lifetime practices; his death and resurrection episodes. The beingness of gender discrimination and supremacy that exist in community settings and even within the religious organisation is a huge arraignment to the institution and everything it meant for in the society. Additionally, this write up recognizes all the endeavors which the Faith Based Institutions are employing to exterminate these practices in its folds. This article attests that what has been done so far is not sufficient to warrant a free gender inequality globe, hence a lot needs to be worked on. It illuminated the impediments regarding the Church's endeavor to confront this abnormality in totality. Based on this, this paper emphasises that gender oppression and discrimination must be preserved in the life and charter of the Church as one of its precedencies. For the Church to be more unequivocal in preaching and practice, every member should be empowered to fight the vagrancy of gender domination and discrimination at all cost.

References

- Ali, T.S., 2021, 'Gender roles and their influence on life prospects for women in urban Karachi, Pakistan: A qualitative study', *Globe health Action* 4(1), 7448. <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v4i0.7448>
- Ayuba, N., 2019, *Women ordination revisited*, West African Association of Theological Institutions (WAATI), SNAAP Press Ltd., Enugu.
- Bako, M.J. & Syed, J., 2018, *Women's marginalization in Nigeria and the way forward, human resource development international*, (viewed 23/05/2024), from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324256804-Women's-marginalization-in-Nigeria-and-the-way-forward>.

Bawa, S., 2017, Christianity, Tradition and Gender Inequality in post-colonial Ghana. *African Geographical Review*. (Accessed on 09/06/2024)

Carbajal, J., 2020, 'Patriarchal culture's influence on women's leadership ascendancy', *The Journal of Faith, Education and Community* 2(1), 2

Charamba, G., Chikwati, T. and Chidarikire, M. 2024, Gender Equality and Women Empowerment. The Case of ZAOGA FIF in Masvingo City, Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Social Studies*, Vol 10 issue 6. (Accessed on 20/08/24)

Charamba, G., 2015, 'Influence of Religion on gender equality and women empowerment in Zimbabwe. The case of ZAOGA Church in Masvingo Urban. Unpublished Masters Thesis, Department of Development Studies, Lupane State University, Bulawayo.

Chinweizu, I., 2019, *Anatomy of female power: A masculinity dissection of matriarchy*, Pero Press, Lagos.

Doctor, H.V., 2020, Women's Schooling and Religious Affiliation in Malawi at the end of 20th Century. *International Journal of Educational Development*, Vol 25:2013, pp 481-492. (Viewed on 09/06/2024)

Ellicott's Commentary for English Readers, 2004, *Galatians 3:28*, viewed 10 August 2021, from <https://biblehub.com/commentaries/galatians/3-28.html>.

Fapohunda, T.M., 2020, 'Gender and development: Challenges to women involvement in Nigeria's development', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences* 2(6), 19.

Gasque, W.W., 2020, 'The role of women in the church, in society and in the home', *Priscilla Papers* 2(2), 1.

Hadebe, N., 2021, 'Gender, gender equality, and the Church', in *Ecumenical women at the United Nations*, (viewed 06 /06/ 2024), from <https://ecumenicalwomen.Org/theology/>.

Jacqueline, M.M., 2019, *Women seeking justice, a life experience and scripture – Based resource book for Christian women's groups*, Paulines Publications Africa, Nairobi.

John Paul II, 1981, 'On the occasion of the concert of the Polish Philharmonic of Zielona Góra (December 31, 1981)', *Vatican*, (viewed 29 January 2022), from <https://www.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/speeches/1981/december.index.html>.

John Paul II, 1988, 'Visit to the Centre for Assistance in "Via degli Astalli" (December 31, 1988)', *Vatican*, (viewed 29/05/2024), from <https://www.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/speeches/1988/december.index.html>.

Joynes, C., 2019, *Women and Christianity*, (viewed 03/04/2024), from <https://www.bl.uk/sacred-texts/articles/women-and-Christianity>.

Klingorova, K. & Havlíček, T., 2020, 'Religion and gender inequality: The status of women in the societies of world religions', *Moravian Geographical Reports* 23(2), 2–11. <https://doi.org/10.1515/mgr-2015-0006>

Maal, B and Banda, H., 2019, *The Norwegian Support to Women's Empowerment and Gender Equality in Zimbabwe. Mapping of actors and priority issues*. SAPES, Harare.

Mabhunu, L., 2020, *Revolting against the Biblical and Traditional Stereotypes of Women Prophets in African Instituted Churches (AICs): The role and place of religion in Harare*. Swedish Press, Uppsala. (Online), (Accessed on 09/06/2024)

Mapuranga, T.P., 2020, *Politics of Pentecostalism and Women Ministries in Zimbabwe: An Interpretation of 1 Corinthians 14:34-35 and 1 Timothy 2:11-14*. University of Bamberg Press, Bamberg

Mwije, S., 2019, 'Religious based gender equality, the role of Christianity in enhancing gender equality in African society', 1(1), 41–53.

Okeke, F.C., 2020, 'Towards maintaining gender equity for sustainable development in Nigeria', *Journal of International Gender Studies* 7(1), 134–158.

Okoli, A.B., 2020, 'The role of Christianity and African traditional religion, among the Northern Igbo of Nigeria', <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts>.

Onwunta, I.E., 2020, 'Gender stereotyping in church and community: A Nigerian feminine perspective', PhD thesis, Department of Practical Theology and Missiology, University of Stellenbosch.

Orji, N., Orji, C. & Agbanyim, O., 2018, *Women's political representation in Nigeria: Why progress is slow and what can be done to fast track it*, (viewed 12/05/2022), from <https://placng.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Women-Political-Representation-pdf>.

Pemunta, N.V. & Alubafi, M.F., 2016, 'The social context of widowhood rights and women's human rights in Cameroon', *Cogent Social Sciences* 2(1), 1234671.

Ram, U., Strohschein, L. & Gaur, K., 2019, 'Gender socialization: Differences between male and female youth in India and associations with mental health', *International Journal of Population Research* 1(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/357145> Slick, M., 2008, *What is Christianity?*, (viewed 27/05/2024), from <https://carm.org/what-is-christianity>.

Sibani, C.M., 2017, 'Gender inequality and its challenge to women development in Nigeria: The religious approach', *Unizik Journal of Arts* 23(1), 432–448.

Tijani, K.D., 1998, 'Perspective of women's reproductive health and rights', *The Post Express* 28, 22.

Uchem, R., 2020, *Over-coming women's subordination: An Igbo African and Christian perspective envisioning and inclusive theology with reference to women*, Snap Press Ltd., Enugu.

Virginia, P., 2019, 'Sex vs. Gender', *International Journal of Transgenderism* 8(4), 29–32. https://doi.org/10.1300/J485v08n04_05

Waters, M., 2018, 'Patriarchy and hierarchy: An exploration and reconstruction of concepts of masculine domination', *Sociology* 3(2), 193–211. <https://>